

ENHANCING THE ENERGY STORAGE CAPABILITY OF LIGNIN BASED CARBON FIBRE VIA SURFACE MODIFICATION

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ABSTRACT

The development of sustainable, multifunctional carbon fibre (CF) composites for structural energy storage is critical for the advancement of lightweight, energy-efficient technologies. Here, we report the surface functionalization of lignin–polyacrylonitrile (PAN) hybrid carbon fibres (LCF) with poly(o-phenylenediamine) (PoPD) via electrochemical grafting using diazonium chemistry, to enhance their electrochemical properties while preserving mechanical performance. The resulting LCF-oPD fibres exhibited a significant enhancement in energy storage behaviour, achieving a specific capacitance of 9.06 F g^{-1} at 1 mV s^{-1} , an 18-fold increase compared to unmodified LCF (0.48 F g^{-1}). Cyclic voltammetry revealed distinct redox peaks for LCF-oPD indicative of the reversible redox reaction of p-quinonediimine units, while galvanostatic charge–discharge cycling over 5000 cycles showed excellent electrochemical stability, with 100% capacitance retention and $\sim 100\%$ coulombic efficiency. Despite the addition of the PoPD layer, mechanical testing showed no statistically significant difference in tensile strength (LCF: $1.86 \pm 0.38 \text{ GPa}$; LCF-oPD: $2.04 \pm 0.33 \text{ GPa}$) or Young’s modulus (LCF: $186.77 \pm 14.58 \text{ GPa}$; LCF-oPD: $192.54 \pm 17.96 \text{ GPa}$). Weibull analysis indicated a slight reduction in failure uniformity (shape parameter decreased from 5.82 to 5.15) but a marginal increase in scale parameter (from 2.01 GPa to 2.20 GPa), suggesting improved strength distribution. These values, although lower than those of conventional PAN-derived CFs (typically $\sim 4 \text{ GPa}$ strength and $\sim 275 \text{ GPa}$ modulus), validate the non-destructive nature of the surface modification. This work demonstrates a scalable strategy for integrating electrochemical functionality into lignin-based CFs without compromising structural integrity, advancing their potential in structural supercapacitor applications and sustainable multifunctional composites.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fibre composites are used increasingly across diverse industries such as aerospace, wind energy and automotive owing to their exceptional strength-to-weight ratio[1-5]. In the automotive sector, carbon fibre reinforced polymers (CFRPs) are particularly attractive because they can significantly reduce vehicle weight by up to 60%, which directly improves fuel economy[6]. However, widespread applications of CFRPs is hindered by their high production costs, largely stemming from the price of the petroleum-based precursors like polyacrylonitrile (PAN) and mesoporous pitch, which account for over half the cost of carbon fibre manufacturing[7]. To overcome this, alternative precursors such as lignin and silk are being explored[7-9]. Lignin in particular is gaining attention due to its abundance, high carbon content, renewable nature and availability as a low-cost by-product from the paper and biofuel industries[10-13]. As industries move towards more sustainable and circular practices, developing multifunctional carbon fibres, especially those capable of energy storage has become a key priority. The world Economic Forum’s “Top 10 Emerging Technologies of 2025” includes structural battery composites as a transformative innovation, highlighting the growing importance of materials that can simultaneously provide mechanical strength and store energy[14]. Achieving this requires a combination

of functional materials, sustainable feedstock and scalable manufacturing approaches, which is a significant challenge.

Lignin-derived carbon materials have been extensively explored for energy storage applications[15-19], particularly in the form of carbon nanospheres[20], nanosheets[21], and nanofibers[22]. These nanostructured forms typically offer high surface areas and can be engineered with various heteroatom dopants (e.g., N, S, O)[23] to enhance electrical conductivity, wettability, and charge storage capacity. Such materials have demonstrated promising electrochemical performance, particularly in electric double-layer capacitors (EDLCs) and pseudocapacitive systems. However, these lignin-based carbons are primarily developed for non-structural applications and often lack the mechanical integrity required for multifunctional systems. In contrast, when lignin is used as a precursor for structural carbon fibres, particularly in combination with polyacrylonitrile (PAN) to form hybrid precursors, the resulting carbon fibres are optimized for mechanical strength and stiffness [24, 25]. This necessitates processing conditions that minimize porosity and surface area, which, while beneficial for structural performance, significantly limits the fibres' ability to store charge via EDLC mechanisms. Consequently, these fibres exhibit relatively poor electrochemical capacitance when directly employed as electrodes in supercapacitor applications. Although the presence of residual oxygen-containing functional groups, such as quinones, may contribute to limited pseudocapacitive behaviour [26], the effect is typically negligible and insufficient for practical energy storage.

These limitations underscore the need for the incorporation of additional electrochemically active materials to enhance the performance of lignin-based structural carbon fibers. Surface functionalization, nanoparticle deposition, or the integration of conductive polymers and metal oxides are promising strategies to synergistically improve the electrochemical activity without compromising the structural integrity of the fibre [27-32]. Such multifunctional modifications are essential for advancing the use of lignin-based carbon fibres in structural energy storage systems.

In this work, we address this challenge by using a lignin-PAN hybrid carbon fibres as a sustainable platform for structural energy storage applications. Specifically, we functionalize the surface of these carbon fibres with the conductive polymer poly(o-phenylenediamine) via reductive diazonium chemistry through a scalable modification strategy to enhance their electrochemical activity while preserving their structural characteristics. The surface modification introduces redox-active and conductive functionalities, increasing the fibre's interfacial capacitance and enabling faradaic or pseudocapacitive charge storage behaviour. This approach not only improves energy storage performance but also maintains compatibility with standard composite manufacturing processes, making it suitable for real-world structural supercapacitor integration. Our strategy demonstrates a pathway toward high-performance, multifunctional composites that align with both sustainability and performance goals, thereby advancing the practical implementation of structural energy storage systems based on renewable carbon fibre sources

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

All reagents and chemicals used in this study were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Australia), and were used without further purification, except for 4-nitobenzene diazonium tetrafluoroborate (NBD) which was synthesized as explained below. The resulting fibres were collected after carbonization for use in this study, prior to undergoing any surface treatment.

2.2 Synthesis of 4-nitobenzene diazonium tetrafluoroborate (NBD)

The synthesis of NBD was achieved rapidly by a one-step synthesis method, where 4-nitroaniline is reacted with nitrosonium tetrafluoroborate (NOBF₄) in a molar ratio of 1:1.2 in dry acetonitrile in a 2-neck round bottom flask under N₂. A typical synthesis used approximately 1 g of total reactants because of the high reactivity of aryldiazonium salts. First, 4 mL of dry acetonitrile was cooled to -40 °C using a cooling bath containing acetonitrile and liquid N₂. The required amount of NOBF₄ was added to cold acetonitrile in 2-neck RBF with minimum exposure to air during transfer. The solution was cooled to -40 °C while stirring. The amine was added to the solution and stirred for 30 min. The RBF was then

taken out of the cooling bath and allowed to warm to room temperature while stirring for another 30 min. The desired diazonium salt product was precipitated out of ice-cold diethyl ether. The precipitated pure product was collected by filtering at the pump and stored under N₂. Purity of the synthesized diazonium salts was determined using ¹H NMR and ¹⁹F NMR and was consistent with literature reports[27].

2.3 Electrochemical modification of carbon fiber

Electrochemical modification of CF was carried out according to literature reports[30]. The set up consisted of a standard three electrode cell with a lignin carbon fibre tow (**LCF**) as the working electrode, a platinum mesh (2.5 cm²) as the counter electrode and a leakless Ag/AgCl reference electrode (ET069-1, eDAQ) immersed in a grafting solution consisted of 20 mM o-PD and 2 mM NBD dissolved in 4:1 deionized water:ethanol solution containing 0.6 M H₂SO₄. Electrochemical grafting procedure was carried out using potentiostatic cyclic voltammetry from -1.0 V to +1.0 V (vs Ag/AgCl) for 10 potential sweep cycles at 10 mV/s with an Autolab PGSTAT204 potentiostat. Measurements were recorded using NOVA 2.0 software. Once the electro-grafting is complete, modified CF tow (**LCF-oPD**) was washed sequentially with chloroform, dichloromethane, ethanol, and acetone to remove any physisorbed materials or excess monomers, followed by drying under reduced pressure to remove any adsorbed solvent on CF surface.

2.4 Characterization of surface chemistry and morphology

A Bruker Alpha FTIR (Bremen, Germany) equipped with a germanium crystal in the attenuated total reflectance (ATR) mode was used for FTIR spectroscopic analysis. The measurements were acquired from 600 to 4000 cm⁻¹ using an average of 32 scans per measurement at a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹.

Raman spectroscopy was performed using Renishaw Raman InVia Confocal Microscope. Equipped with an Ar⁺ laser with an excitation wavelength of 514 nm (50 mW) and a diffraction grating of 2400 mm⁻¹. After calibrating the instrument using a silica reference, spectra were obtained between 800 and 2100 cm⁻¹ with an average of 5 accumulations at an exposure time of 1 s.

SEM imaging was performed on a JEOL JSM 7800F at an electron accelerating voltage (electron high tension) of 5 kV. CF samples were mounted to an aluminium pin stub using double sided carbon tape. Imaging was performed without any conductive coating to enhance the visualization.

2.5 Characterization of electrochemical properties

Electrochemical tests were carried out using a BioLogic SP-300 electrochemical station at room temperature. Cyclic voltammetry (CV), Galvanostatic charge-discharge (GCD) and Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) of functionalized CF (tow) electrodes were tested in a three-electrode cell set up with a leak-less Ag/AgCl reference electrode (ET069-1, eDAQ) and a graphite rod counter electrode in 1 M H₂SO₄ electrolyte. EIS was performed at a frequency between 10 mHz and 100 kHz with 10 points per decade and an amplitude of 10 mV. For the SSC device, measurements were conducted in a two-electrode set up. All electrochemical data was analyzed using EC-Lab v11.42 software according to previously published reports using the following equations.

The CF electrodes were tested at 100, 50, 20, 10, 5 and 1 mV s⁻¹ scan rates with an electric potential window of 0.6 V. Specific capacitance values from CV were determined using Equation 1,

$$C_{CV} = \int \frac{I dv}{m v \Delta V} \quad (1)$$

where C_{CV} (F g⁻¹) is the specific capacitance, $\int I dv$ (AV) is the area of the cyclic voltammogram corresponding to discharge processes (*i.e.*, half of total area), m (g) is the CF mass of both electrodes, v (V s⁻¹) is the scan rate, and ΔV (V) is the potential window of the CV.

GCDs were measured at different discharge current densities with an electric potential window of 0.6 V. Specific capacitance values from GCD were determined using Equation 2,

$$C_{GCD} = \left(\frac{I_D}{m} \right) \frac{t_D}{\Delta V - V_{IR}} \quad (2)$$

where C_{GCD} ($F g^{-1}$) is the specific capacitance, I_D (A) is the discharge current, t_d (s) is the discharge time, m (g) is the CF mass of both electrodes, and ΔV (V) is the potential window of the GCD test. Since voltage drop due to internal resistance IR (Ω) is inevitable in GCD tests, V_{IR} has been excluded in the calculations for more accurate results due to internal resistance. GCD tests were performed at different discharge currents densities (I_D/m) ($A g^{-1}$).

For electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) experiments the frequency was swept from between 10 mHz to 100 kHz with 10 points per decade and a sinus amplitude of 10 mV. EIS data was analysed and circuit Zfit (Figure S8) performed using EC-Lab v11.42 software.

2.6 Characterization of surface mechanical properties

Single filament characterization for surface modified CF was carried out on a Favimat + Robot 2 (Textechno) single fibre tester. This instrument automatically measures the linear density, diameter, tensile strength and elastic modulus of individual carbon fibre and was equipped with a 210 cN load cell. A pre-tension of 0.5 cN was applied to align the fibres before testing. Linear density of each fibre was determined via vibrospectroscopy and then a tensile load was applied to the fibres until fibre failure. A minimum of 75 individual filaments were analyzed to provide a high degree of confidence in the results.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Surface chemistry and morphology

The electrochemical surface modification of LCF was directly translated from our previous works using pristine T300 CF that was spun using a PAN precursor [27, 30]. Aryl diazonium salts have proven highly effective in our work for forming stable covalent bonds with the carbon fibre surface, and in this case, they act as anchoring sites to facilitate the subsequent oxidative polymerisation of PoPD. The proposed electrochemical grafting mechanism and the anticipated surface chemistry of LCF-oPD are illustrated in Figure 1(a). The representative cyclic voltammogram (Figure 1(b)) clearly shows the distinct reduction of the diazonium salt and the oxidation of o-phenylenediamine, leading to the formation of radical species involved in the grafting process.

SEM has been utilized to study the unique surface topographical features on LCF surfaces before and after functionalization. As shown in Figure 1(c), the SEM image of the LCF surface displays a relatively smooth texture, in contrast to the PAN-based T300 carbon fibres, which typically exhibit striations and microgrooved surface features. Following surface modification, the SEM image of LCF-oPD (Figure 1(d)) reveals a markedly altered surface morphology, characterized by a consistent coating of polymeric material. This uniform coating represents a significant improvement compared to the same polymer applied to T300 carbon fibres, where the surface coverage was noticeably less consistent [27, 30, 33]. We previously attributed this to the heterogeneous surface chemistry of T300 CF, which likely influences local conductivity across the fibre. Four-point probe measurements indicated that the electrical conductivity of the LCF ($438.62 S cm^{-1}$) was lower than that of T300 CFs ($884.88 S cm^{-1}$); however, the more uniform surface chemistry of LCF may compensate for this by enabling more homogeneous electrochemical grafting. This could facilitate even attachment of the NBD priming layer, subsequently promoting uniform oxidative polymerization of oPD.

As shown in Figure 1(e), FTIR spectrum of LCF-oPD shows distinct peaks at $1636 cm^{-1}$, $1161 cm^{-1}$, $1041 cm^{-1}$ and $865 cm^{-1}$ ascribed to C=N stretching in quinoid ring, C-N stretching in benzenoid units, C-N stretching and out-of-plane bending motions of C-H of 1,2,4-trisubstituted benzene nuclei, respectively[33]. Therefore, the spectral data obtained were in good agreement with the expected structure of o-phenylenediamine. The Raman spectra of LCF and LCF-oPD reveal notable differences in the D to G band intensity ratios (I_D/I_G), which provide insights into the structural ordering of the carbon fibre surface (Figure 1(f)). For LCF-oPD, the (I_D/I_G), ratio is higher (1.04) compared to that of pristine LCF (1.00), indicating an increase in structural disorder and the presence of more amorphous carbon on the surface. This change suggests that the surface modification process, involving the oxidative polymerization of o-phenylenediamine, introduces additional defect sites and disrupts the graphitic ordering of the carbon fibre surface, consistent with the formation of a polymeric coating.

Figure 1: (a) The reaction mechanism for surface modification of LCF and expected surface chemistry on LCF-oPD, (b) a representative CV for the electrochemical surface modification with oPD (c) SEM of LCF (d) SEM of LCF-oPD (e) FTIR spectra for LCF and LCF-oPD and (f) Raman spectra for LCF and LCF-oPD

3.2 Energy storage

The electrochemical properties of LCF and LCF-oPD electrodes were explored in an aqueous electrolyte (1M H₂SO₄) to understand the electrochemical performance. Cyclic voltammetry (CV) and galvanostatic charge discharge (GCD) experiments have been conducted at different scan rates and current densities, respectively. The overall capacitance of LCF-oPD is a combination of electric double layer capacitance (EDLC) and pseudocapacitance from oPD.

Representative cyclic voltammograms (CVs) recorded at a scan rate of 20 mV s⁻¹ are presented in Figure 2(a). The CV trace for LCF-oPD exhibits pronounced redox peaks characteristic of the electroactive polymer, along with a broad enclosed area indicative of enhanced charge storage capacity. Each cyclic voltammogram features a pair of redox peaks corresponding to reversible redox reaction of p-quinonediazine units accompanied by the transfer of two electrons and two protons [27]

In contrast, the CV of unmodified LCF displays a featureless, nearly linear profile with a minimal enclosed area, suggesting negligible capacitive behavior. These observations are further corroborated by the galvanostatic charge–discharge (GCD) curves shown in Figure 2(b). The GCD profile of LCF shows a steep and rapid voltage response, whereas the LCF-oPD curve demonstrates an extended, more gradual charging and discharging behavior, consistent with faradaic processes. The specific capacitance values calculated across different scan rates are summarized in Table 1 and Figure 2(c), further highlighting the superior electrochemical performance of the surface-functionalized fibres. At 1 mV/s LCF-oPD demonstrated a specific capacitance of 9.06 F/g which is a ~18x improvement compared to the capacitance of LCF which was only 0.48 F/g at the same scan rate.

Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) analysis revealed that LCF-oPD exhibits a higher equivalent series resistance (ESR) compared to unmodified LCF. This increase is likely attributed to the introduction of the poly(o-phenylenediamine) (PoPD) layer at the fibre interface, which, despite being conductive, may introduce interfacial resistance during initial formation. To assess the long-term electrochemical stability of these electrodes, galvanostatic charge–discharge (GCD) cycling was performed over 5000 cycles. The LCF electrode initially retained 100% of its discharge capacitance; however, its performance steadily declined, retaining only 69% after 5000 cycles. In contrast, the LCF-oPD electrode exhibited a gradual increase in capacitance retention, reaching and maintaining 100% by the end of the test. This trend suggests that the PoPD layer undergoes an electrochemical conditioning process, progressively improving its performance until it reaches a stable, optimized state. Additionally, the coulombic efficiency of the LCF electrode exceeded 100%, indicative of a faster or more immediate discharge process relative to charging, possibly due to surface-related parasitic effects. In contrast, LCF-oPD maintained a consistent coulombic efficiency of approximately 100% throughout cycling, highlighting its excellent electrochemical reversibility and long-term stability.

Table 1: Specific capacitance values for LCF and LCF-oPD at different scan rates and current densities

Scan rate (mV/s)	Specific capacitance (F/g)		Current density (mA/g)	Specific capacitance (F/g)	
	LCF	LCF-oPD		LCF	LCF-oPD
50	0.06	4.85	100	0.06	6.82
20	0.08	7.01	75	0.04	7.09
10	0.10	7.52	50	0.03	7.91
5	0.14	7.86	25	0.04	9.89
1	0.48	9.06	10	0.07	2.79

Figure 2: (a) Representative CVs of LCF and LCF-oPD done at 20 mV/s (b) Representative GCDs of LCF and LCF-oPD at 0.05 A/g (c) A graph of Specific capacitance vs the scan rate for LCF and LF-oPD (d) Nyquist plots for LCF and LCF-oPD (e) Discharge capacitance retention of LCF and LF-oPD electrodes during 5000 charge-discharge cycles (f) Coulombic efficiency of LCF and LCF-oPD during 5000 charge-discharge cycles (inset: SEM of LCF-oPD before and after cycling)

3.3 Mechanical properties

The graph presents a comparative analysis of the tensile strength and Young's modulus of LCF and LCF-oPD samples. Although the LCF-oPD samples exhibit marginally higher mean values for both tensile strength (2.04 GPa vs. 1.86 GPa) and Young's modulus (192.54 GPa vs. 186.77 GPa) relative to the unmodified LCF, the error (typically derived from inhomogeneous distribution of flaws along the fibre) indicate that these differences are not statistically significant. This suggests that the surface modification using oPD does not detrimentally affect the mechanical integrity of the LCF, confirming the non-destructive nature of the treatment. Nonetheless, both strength and modulus values are considerably lower than those of conventional PAN-derived carbon fibers, which typically demonstrate tensile strengths around 4 GPa and moduli near 275 GPa. This further underscores the need to balance functionality and mechanical performance in modified or recycled carbon fibers.

Figure 3: Comparison of tensile strength and Young's modulus of LCF and LCF-oPD

The Weibull shape parameter describes the variability of failure in a material and the scale parameter represents the strength of the fibre. A decrease in shape parameter was observed upon electrochemical functionalization of LCF with oPD (Table 2). A decrease in the shape parameter indicates more variability in terms of failure properties of the fibre, proving the fibres are slightly less consistent in terms of failure properties after surface modification. However, the Weibull scale parameter suggests an increase in the overall strength of the fibre after surface modification. Overall, the Weibull parameters suggest a less uniform failure behavior, with an increase in the overall strength after surface modification, but the average tensile strength increase is statistically insignificant.

Table 2: Mechanical properties and Weibull parameters for LCF and LCF-oPD

	Tensile strength (GPa)	Young's modulus (GPa)	Weibull shape parameter	Weibull scale parameter (GPa)
LCF	1.86 ± 0.38	186.77 ± 14.58	5.82	2.01
LCF-oPD	2.04 ± 0.33	192.54 ± 17.96	5.15	2.2

4 CONCLUSIONS

This study demonstrates the successful surface modification of lignin-PAN hybrid carbon fibers (LCF) with poly(o-phenylenediamine) (PoPD) via a scalable electrochemical diazonium grafting strategy, enabling significant enhancement of their electrochemical performance while retaining mechanical integrity. The modified LCF-oPD electrodes exhibited a substantial increase in specific

capacitance (9.06 F g^{-1} at 1 mV s^{-1}) compared to unmodified LCF (0.48 F g^{-1}) and maintained excellent cycling stability and coulombic efficiency over 5000 charge–discharge cycles. Mechanical characterization revealed no statistically significant deterioration in tensile strength or modulus following modification, confirming the non-destructive nature of the treatment.

However, the inherently lower mechanical properties of LCF ($1.86 \pm 0.38 \text{ GPa}$ tensile strength, $186.77 \pm 14.58 \text{ GPa}$ modulus) compared to conventional PAN-derived CFs ($\sim 4 \text{ GPa}$, $\sim 275 \text{ GPa}$) limit their use in high-performance structural applications. Despite this, the incorporation of multifunctionality through surface engineering makes LCF a viable candidate for structural energy storage composites, particularly where moderate mechanical demands coexist with the need for embedded energy storage. Moreover, the conductive polymer coating introduced via electrochemical grafting provides a versatile platform for further functionalization, such as the integration of MXenes or the assembly of multilayer structures with other polymers, potentially enhancing both energy storage performance and interfacial adhesion with polymer matrices. This work highlights a pathway toward sustainable, multifunctional carbon fiber composites by leveraging bio-derived precursors and advanced surface modification strategies.

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